

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

ANALYZING DIFFERENT MARKETING FRAMEWORKS FOR DIGITAL PRODUCTS AND SERVICES

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Abstract

This study conducts a comparative analysis of three prominent marketing models (12P, 4A, and SIVA) to assess their applicability for promoting digital products and services. By examining various examples, the research highlights the strengths and weaknesses of each model. The findings provide valuable insights for enterprises seeking to optimize their marketing strategies in the dynamic digital marketplace.

Keywords: marketing, digital product, marketplace, SIVA model, 12P model, 4A model.

1. INTRODUCTION

The surge in digital technology has fundamentally reshaped the marketing arena, prompting an inquiry into the effectiveness of established marketing models for digital products and services (Kotler et al., 2017). Digital products, uniquely capable of being transacted and delivered through online platforms (Kumar & Reinartz, 2012), stand in stark contrast to physical commodities that require tangible logistics (Mangold & Faulds, 2009).

Given the distinct economic and physical properties of digital products, a shift in conventional marketing strategies is necessitated. Their transactional nature, independent of a physical medium and with near-zero distribution and production costs, ushers in a new era where traditional pricing strategies may not hold (Chaffey & Ellis-Chadwick, 2012). This creates a debate around the applicability of established models like the 12P model (Low & Tan, 1995). While comprehensive, the 12P model was originally designed for physical goods, leading to doubts about its effectiveness in the digital realm.

Simultaneously, the 4A model (Jagdish, 2003), which focuses on consumer perspectives (Acceptability, Affordability, Accessibility, Awareness), offers another lens through which to view this shift. Despite its widespread recognition, it's unclear whether this model effectively addresses the evolving needs and behaviors of consumers of digital products.

The SIVA model (Smith, 2004), emphasizing the Solution, Information, Value, and Access aspects from a consumer's perspective, offers an alternative framework for analyzing the purchasing process. Although it has a sound theoretical foundation, the effectiveness of the SIVA model in marketing digital products remains unproven.

Thus, this research aims to conduct an in-depth analysis of these three marketing models—12P, 4A, and SIVA—in the context of digital products and services. By investigating their strengths, weaknesses, and overall applicability, the study seeks to provide invaluable insights for enterprises seeking to optimize their digital marketing strategies (Kotler & Armstrong, 2010).

The decision to choose the 12P, 4A, and SIVA models for this research was driven by several factors:

Comprehensiveness: The models collectively cover a wide range of marketing aspects, which makes them suitable for a comprehensive analysis of different digital products and services. The 12P model covers various elements beyond the traditional 4Ps of marketing (Product, Price, Place, Promotion) to include elements like People, Process, Partnerships, Performance, Positioning, etc., making it a comprehensive tool for product and service analysis. The 4A and SIVA models, while more consumer-focused, provide an additional layer of depth by considering customers' perspectives, which is crucial in today's customer-centric marketplace.

Versatility: These models are versatile and can be applied to a wide variety of businesses and industries, making them suitable for analyzing different types of digital products and services.

Complementarity: While each model can stand on its own, they also complement each other quite well. The 12P model is more business-oriented and focuses on product/service design and delivery aspects, while the 4A and SIVA models are consumer-oriented and emphasize understanding and meeting consumer needs. This balance allows for a holistic approach to marketing strategy analysis that considers both the business and customer perspectives.

Relevance to Digital Products/Services: These models are highly relevant for analyzing digital products and services. For instance, the 'Physical Evidence' component of the 12P model can be adapted to consider digital interfaces and user experiences, the 'Access' aspect of the 4A model can be linked to digital accessibility, and the 'Information' part of the SIVA model is especially relevant in the context of digital products/services, where information provision is often a critical factor.

Broad Acceptance and Use: The chosen models are well-established and widely used in the field of marketing. Their broad acceptance and use indicate their utility and effectiveness, making them suitable choices for this research.

By using these three models, the research aims to provide a robust and nuanced analysis of marketing strategies for various digital products and services. It seeks to offer valuable insights for businesses looking to optimize their marketing strategies in the increasingly digital and customer-centric marketplace.

2. DIGITAL PRODUCTS AND SERVICES: CHARACTERISTICS AND CATEGORIES:

The advent of digital technology has revolutionized the way we interact with products and services. Our economy has shifted from a traditional material-centric model to one that prioritizes digital products and services, hence a comprehensive study of their characteristics and categories becomes imperative. This literature review explores the works of different authors who have contributed significantly to understanding digital products and services.

2.1 Characteristics of Digital Products and Services

Intangibility: In their seminal work, George & Kumar(2018) explain that digital products and services are intangible, meaning they can't be physically touched or seen before purchasing. This, in turn, demands novel strategies for marketing and customer service.

Scalability: Amit and Zott (2012) argue that digital products and services are highly scalable. Once created, these can be duplicated and distributed to an unlimited number of users without incremental costs.

Instant Delivery: Lindsay and Shell(2019) argue that digital products and services can be delivered instantly over the internet. This attribute brings a new level of convenience for customers and efficiency for businesses.

Personalization: Mayer-Schönberger and Cukier(2013) elaborate on the capability of digital products to be highly personalized. With the aid of artificial intelligence and machine learning, digital services can be tailored to each user's preferences and behavior.

Interactivity: Toffler (1980) explains that digital products and services often afford interactive experiences. Unlike traditional products, they allow consumers to participate in, manipulate, or control the product or service.

Connectivity: According to Chaffey and Ellis-Chadwick (2019), digital products and services are typically connected, allowing real-time updates and improvements. They can also gather user data to further enhance the experience and customization.

Perishability: Kalyanam and McIntyre (2020) highlight that unlike physical goods, digital products and services often have a limited lifespan. This can be due to rapid technological advancements, changing consumer preferences, or the ephemeral nature of certain digital services.

Dependency on Technology: Parker, Van Alstyne, and Choudary(2016) point out that digital products and services are dependent on technology for delivery and consumption. This implies a reliance on internet connectivity and suitable hardware/software for users.

2.2 Categories of Digital Products and Services

Digital Media Products: According to George & Kumar (2018), digital media products constitute a significant category. This includes eBooks, music, films, and software. Such products can be sold individually, as subscriptions, or even streamed online.

Online Services: Amit and Zott (2012) consider online services a dominant category in the digital landscape. These encompass diverse sectors such as finance (online banking, investment platforms), education (e-learning platforms), and entertainment (streaming services).

Digital Tools and Platforms: As per Lindsay and Shell (2019), digital tools and platforms, like cloud storage services, digital design tools, or social media platforms, form an essential category of digital services. These tools enable businesses and individuals to accomplish tasks more efficiently.

Data and Analytics Services: Mayer-Schönberger and Cukier (2013) emphasize the rising significance of data and analytics services. These provide insights from large datasets, helping businesses make more informed decisions.

Software as a Service (SaaS): Parker, Van Alstyne, and Choudary (2016) emphasize the significance of SaaS. This includes services such as customer relationship management tools, project management tools, and other business productivity tools delivered over the internet.

E-commerce Services: In "The New Marketing Analytics" (2020), Kalyanam and McIntyre talk about the rise of e-commerce services, where physical goods are sold through digital platforms. This includes online marketplaces and digital storefronts.

Social Media Services: According to Chaffey and Ellis-Chadwick (2019), social media services are integral to the digital landscape. They facilitate networking, content sharing, and are increasingly used for commercial purposes.

Gaming Services: Toffler (1980) was one of the earliest to recognize the potential of digital games. Today, online games, esports, and mobile gaming apps form a significant part of the digital service sector.

The characteristics and categories of digital products and services represent an intricate and ever-evolving landscape. They are, without doubt, pivotal to our increasingly digital economy. As more businesses transition towards digital offerings, understanding these components will be essential to leverage the benefits of digitalization.

The following table 1. presents a comprehensive overview of the key characteristics that define digital products and services. Organized into four distinct categories, this table sheds light on the inherent attributes, user-centric features, technological dependencies, and temporal characteristics that shape the digital landscape. By understanding these fundamental aspects, we can gain valuable insights into the unique nature of digital offerings and their impact on various aspects of company's operations.

Table 1.

Key characteristics of digital products and services¹

Attributes	Categories			
	1: Inherent Attributes	2: User-Centric Features	3: Technological Dependencies	4: Temporal Characteristics
	Intangibility	Personalization	Connectivity	Perishability
	Scalability	Interactivity	Dependency on Technology	Limited Lifespan
	Instant Delivery	User Control	Real-time Updates	

3. MARKETING STRATEGY FOR DIGITAL PRODUCTS AND SERVICES

In marketing, various models can be used to analyze and construct effective marketing strategies. Three of the more common models include the 12P, 4A, and SIVA models. Understanding these frameworks can help us understand the similarities and differences in their approach and effectiveness for different digital products and services.

12P Model. The 12P model is an extended version of the traditional 4P model (Product, Price, Place, Promotion) incorporating more variables. These are Product, Price, Place, Promotion, People, Process, Physical evidence, Philosophy, Partners, Performance, Position, and Packaging.

In the context of digital products and services, these elements shape the strategy as follows:

Product: The definition of what's being sold; in digital products, this could range from software to a digital subscription or an online course.

Price: Refers to the pricing strategy considering costs, competition, and customer willingness to pay. Digital products often adopt different pricing models, like subscription-based or one-time payment.

Place: In digital marketing, place refers to the channels used to reach the customers. These can include websites, social media platforms, email marketing, etc.

Promotion: This involves communicating with the target audience using techniques like content marketing, SEO, email marketing, social media marketing, or PPC advertising.

People: Refers to the individuals involved in the delivery and consumption of services. In digital marketing, this could mean the team behind the product/service or the influencers who promote it.

Process, Physical evidence, Philosophy, Partners, Performance, Position, Packaging: These elements relate to the customer journey, brand values, strategic alliances, overall efficiency, market standing, and presentation of the product respectively.

4A Model. The 4A model (Acceptability, Affordability, Accessibility, and Awareness) represents a more customer-oriented perspective on marketing, compared to the business-centric 4P model.

Acceptability: Refers to how well consumers accept the product/service. This includes product features, quality, and overall customer satisfaction.

Affordability: This is the consumer's perspective on price. The product/service must be priced in a way that customers perceive as fair and affordable.

Accessibility: This relates to the ease with which consumers can obtain the product/service. In digital products, this might mean the ease of downloading, navigating, and using an app or software.

Awareness: This involves ensuring consumers are aware of the product/service. In digital marketing, this might involve SEO, content marketing, and social media promotions.

SIVA Model. SIVA (Solution, Information, Value, and Access) is another customer-centric marketing model:

Solution: This is about identifying customers' problems and demonstrating how the product/service provides a solution.

Information: Involves providing information about the solution the product/service offers. In digital marketing, this could involve using a blog or social media to provide this information.

Value: This involves demonstrating the value the product/service offers compared to competitors.

Access: This is similar to the "Place" and "Accessibility" concepts in the previous models, emphasizing the ease with which customers can get the product/service.

Differences, Similarities, and Suitability. The 12P model is comprehensive and covers a wide array of factors. It is business-centric, focusing on creating and optimizing the product or service offering. This model would work best for companies aiming for a holistic approach that covers all potential aspects of marketing.

The 4A and SIVA models, on the other hand, focus more on the customer perspective. They prioritize understanding and meeting customer needs and preferences, which can make them more suitable for businesses targeting specific customer segments or niches.

The best model depends on the specific context and goals of the business. Some businesses may find that a combination of models works best for them.

The following table 2. provides a comparative analysis of eight distinct digital service types: Digital Media Products, Online Services, Digital Tools and Platforms, Data and Analytics Services, Software as a Service (SaaS), E-commerce Services, Social Media Services, and Gaming Services. Each service type is examined through the lens of key elements from three well-established marketing models: 12P, 4A, and SIVA.

¹ Authors elaboration

Table 2.

A comparative analysis of eight distinct digital service types²

Service Type	12P (Product)	4A (Acceptability)	SIVA (Solution)
Digital Media Products	Subscription-based model with continuous content updates to maintain customer interest.	High-quality content that meets the entertainment needs of consumers.	Music, eBooks, films, etc., as a solution for entertainment and leisure needs.
Online Services	Personalized services based on individual needs.	High speed and performance of online services.	Tailored services providing convenience (e.g., e-banking, e-learning).
Digital Tools & Platforms	Functional, user-friendly design.	Tools must be intuitive and easy-to-use for the target user group.	Platforms designed to streamline and improve business or personal tasks.
Data & Analytics Services	Highly reliable and accurate data analytics services.	Providing insightful, actionable information.	Businesses gaining insights and making data-driven decisions.
Software as a Service (SaaS)	Highly customizable tools for business productivity.	Seamless integration with existing business systems.	Reducing manual work and increasing efficiency through automation.
E-commerce Services	Wide range of products, easy return policy.	Easy navigation, quick and safe transaction processes.	Providing a convenient shopping experience without leaving home.
Social Media Services	User-friendly interface, personalized content recommendations.	Providing a platform for networking and sharing content.	Creating connections, sharing content, and networking.
Gaming Services	Games with engaging gameplay and continuous updates.	High-quality graphics, engaging storylines, and multiplayer options.	Providing entertainment, leisure, and a sense of community.

This comparative view offers an insightful perspective on the unique characteristics and marketing approaches that can be adopted for each type of digital service. It's crucial to note that this table offers a simplified view. In reality, a comprehensive marketing strategy would delve into each element of these models in greater detail. The aim here is to provide a high-level overview of how these marketing frameworks can be effectively applied across various digital services.

4. DISCUSSION

In the pursuit of effective marketing strategies for digital products and services, a variety of models can serve as useful tools. The choice between using the 12P, 4A, or SIVA model should be guided by the specific context and objectives of the business. Understanding the distinctions between these models and their different focal points can significantly enhance the development of a marketing strategy.

The 12P model, with its broad scope and business-centric perspective, is particularly suitable for organizations seeking a comprehensive approach to their marketing strategy. Its wide array of factors takes into account not only the product or service but also the philosophies, processes, and partnerships that underpin its delivery. Consequently, it proves especially beneficial when launching new ventures or reassessing existing marketing strategies.

The 4A and SIVA models, on the other hand, adopt a customer-centric outlook. They place emphasis on understanding and addressing customer needs and preferences, offering a valuable lens for businesses that wish to align their offerings closely with consumer ex-

pectations. The 4A model can be instrumental in reevaluating a company's position from the customer's viewpoint, while the SIVA model lends itself to industries offering solutions to specific customer problems.

A key insight, however, is that these models are not mutually exclusive. Companies can, and often do, take a hybrid approach, combining elements from different models to create a bespoke strategy. For instance, a firm might utilize the 12P model to design an overarching strategy, then deploy the 4A or SIVA model to ensure alignment with customer needs.

Ultimately, these models are guides, intended to aid the strategic thinking of businesses as they navigate the digital marketplace. By understanding the strengths and nuances of each model, businesses can select the best tools for their needs and craft a marketing strategy that will drive their digital products or services to success.

5. CONCLUSION

This study presents four crucial insights. First, it underscores the distinct attributes of digital products and services, indicating that classic marketing models such as 12P, 4A, and SIVA may need to be interpreted differently given these unique characteristics. Second, it offers a comprehensive analysis of the applicability of these models across a variety of digital product and service categories, supplying marketers with a strategic blueprint. A third key takeaway is the importance of model selection in achieving optimal customer engagement and market penetration. Lastly, the research stresses the need for continuous adaptation and model re-evaluation due to the dynamic nature of the digital

² Authors elaboration

environment, indicating a constant need for marketing innovation.

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